

Some Fixed Point Theorems in Fuzzy n -Normed Spaces

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Abstract: The main purpose of this paper is to study the existence of a fixed points in fuzzy n -normed spaces. we proved our main results, a fixed point theorem for a self mapping and a common fixed point theorem for a pair of weakly compatible mappings on fuzzy n -normed spaces. Also we gave some remarks on fuzzy n -normed spaces.

Key Words: Smarandache space, Pseudo-Euclidean space, fuzzy n -normed spaces, n -seminorm.

AMS(2000): 34A10, 34C10

§1. Introduction

A Pseudo-Euclidean space is a particular Smarandache space defined on a Euclidean space \mathbb{R}^n such that a straight line passing through a point p may turn an angle $\theta_p \geq 0$. If $\theta_p \geq 0$, then p is called a non-Euclidean point. Otherwise, a Euclidean point. In this paper, normed spaces are considered to be Euclidean, i.e., every point is Euclidean. In [7], S. Gähler introduced n -norms on a linear space. A detailed theory of n -normed linear space can be found in [8,10,12-13]. In [8], H. Gunawan and M. Mashadi gave a simple way to derive an $(n-1)$ -norm from the n -norm in such a way that the convergence and completeness in the n -norm is related to those in the derived $(n-1)$ -norm. A detailed theory of fuzzy normed linear space can be found in [1,3,4,5,6,9,11]. In [14], A. Narayanan and S. Vijayabalaji have extend n -normed linear space to fuzzy n -normed linear space. In section 2, we quote some basic definitions, and we show that a fuzzy n -norm is closely related to an ascending system of n -seminorms. In section 3, we introduce a locally convex topology in a fuzzy n -normed space. In section 4, we consider finite dimensional fuzzy n -normed linear spaces. In section 5, we give some fixed point theorem in fuzzy n -normed spaces.

¹Received June 1, 2010. Accepted September 8, 2010.

§2. Fuzzy n -norms and ascending families of n -seminorms

Let n be a positive integer, and let X be a real vector space of dimension at least n . We recall the definitions of an n -seminorm and a fuzzy n -norm [14].

Definition 2.1 A function $(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) \mapsto \|x_1, \dots, x_n\|$ from X^n to $[0, \infty)$ is called an n -seminorm on X if it has the following four properties:

- (S1) $\|x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n\| = 0$ if x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n are linearly dependent;
- (S2) $\|x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n\|$ is invariant under any permutation of x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n ;
- (S3) $\|x_1, \dots, x_{n-1}, cx_n\| = |c| \|x_1, \dots, x_{n-1}, x_n\|$ for any real c ;
- (S4) $\|x_1, \dots, x_{n-1}, y + z\| \leq \|x_1, \dots, x_{n-1}, y\| + \|x_1, \dots, x_{n-1}, z\|$.

An n -seminorm is called a n -norm if $\|x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n\| > 0$ whenever x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n are linearly independent.

Definition 2.1 A fuzzy subset N of $X^n \times \mathbb{R}$ is called a fuzzy n -norm on X if and only if :

- (F1) For all $t \leq 0$, $N(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n, t) = 0$;
- (F2) For all $t > 0$, $N(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n, t) = 1$ if and only if x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n are linearly dependent;
- (F3) $N(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n, t)$ is invariant under any permutation of x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n ;
- (F4) For all $t > 0$ and $c \in \mathbb{R}$, $c \neq 0$,

$$N(x_1, x_2, \dots, cx_n, t) = N(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n, \frac{t}{|c|});$$

- (F5) For all $s, t \in \mathbb{R}$,

$$N(x_1, \dots, x_{n-1}, y + z, s + t) \geq \min \{N(x_1, \dots, x_{n-1}, y, s), N(x_1, \dots, x_{n-1}, z, t)\}.$$

- (F6) $N(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n, t)$ is a non-decreasing function of $t \in \mathbb{R}$ and

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} N(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n, t) = 1.$$

The following two theorems clarify the relationship between Definitions 2, 1 and 2.2.

Theorem 2.1 Let N be a fuzzy n -norm on X . As in [14] define for $x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n \in X$ and $\alpha \in (0, 1)$

$$\|x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n\|_\alpha := \inf \{t : N(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n, t) \geq \alpha\}. \quad (1)$$

Then the following statements hold.

- (A1) For every $\alpha \in (0, 1)$, $\|\bullet, \bullet, \dots, \bullet\|_\alpha$ is an n -seminorm on X ;

(A2) If $0 < \alpha < \beta < 1$ and $x_1, \dots, x_n \in X$ then

$$\|x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n\|_\alpha \leq \|x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n\|_\beta;$$

(A3) If $x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n \in X$ are linearly independent then

$$\lim_{\alpha \rightarrow 1^-} \|x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n\|_\alpha = \infty.$$

Proof (A1) and (A2) are shown in [14, Theorem 3.4]. Let $x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n \in X$ be linearly independent, and $t > 0$ be given. We set $\beta := N(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n, t)$. It follows from (F2) that $\beta \in [0, 1)$. Then (F6) shows that, for $\alpha \in (\beta, 1)$,

$$\|x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n\|_\alpha \geq t.$$

This proves (A3). □

We now prove a converse of Theorem 2.1.

Theorem 2.2 *Suppose we are given a family $\|\bullet, \bullet, \dots, \bullet\|_\alpha$, $\alpha \in (0, 1)$, of n -seminorms on X with properties (A2) and (A3). We define*

$$N(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n, t) := \inf\{\alpha \in (0, 1) : \|x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n\|_\alpha \geq t\}. \quad (2)$$

where the infimum of the empty set is understood as 1. Then N is a fuzzy n -norm on X .

Proof (F1) holds because the values of an n -seminorm are nonnegative.

(F2): Let $t > 0$. If x_1, \dots, x_n are linearly dependent then $N(x_1, \dots, x_n, t) = 1$ follows from property (S1) of an n -seminorm. If x_1, \dots, x_n are linearly independent then $N(x_1, \dots, x_n, t) < 1$ follows from (A3).

(F3) is a consequence of property (S2) of an n -seminorm.

(F4) is a consequence of property (S3) of an n -seminorm.

(F5): Let $\alpha \in (0, 1)$ satisfy

$$\alpha < \min\{N(x_1, \dots, x_{n-1}, y, s), N(x_1, \dots, x_{n-1}, z, s)\}. \quad (3)$$

It follows that $\|x_1, \dots, x_{n-1}, y\|_\alpha < s$ and $\|x_1, \dots, x_{n-1}, z\|_\alpha < t$. Then (S4) gives

$$\|x_1, \dots, x_{n-1}, y + z\|_\alpha < s + t.$$

Using (A2) we find $N(x_1, \dots, x_{n-1}, y + z, s + t) \geq \alpha$ and, since α is arbitrary in (3), (F5) follows.

(F6): Definition 2.2 shows that N is non-decreasing in t . Moreover, $\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} N(x_1, \dots, x_n, t) = 1$ because seminorms have finite values. □

It is easy to see that Theorems 2.1 and 2.2 establish a one-to-one correspondence between fuzzy n -norms with the additional property that the function $t \mapsto N(x_1, \dots, x_n, t)$ is left-continuous for all x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n and families of n -seminorms with properties (A2), (A3) and the additional property that $\alpha \mapsto \|x_1, \dots, x_n\|_\alpha$ is left-continuous for all x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n .

Example 2.3([14,Example 3.3] Let $\|\bullet, \bullet, \dots, \bullet\|$ be a n -norm on X . Define $N(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n, t) = 0$ if $t \leq 0$ and, for $t > 0$,

$$N(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n, t) = \frac{t}{t + \|x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n\|}.$$

Then the seminorms (2.1) are given by

$$\|x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n\|_\alpha = \frac{\alpha}{1 - \alpha} \|x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n\|.$$

§3. The locally convex topology generated by a fuzzy n -norm

In this section (X, N) is a fuzzy n -normed space, that is, X is real vector space and N is fuzzy n -norm on X . We form the family of n -seminorms $\|\bullet, \bullet, \dots, \bullet\|_\alpha$, $\alpha \in (0, 1)$, according to Theorem 2.1. This family generates a family \mathcal{F} of seminorms

$$\|x_1, \dots, x_{n-1}, \bullet\|_\alpha, \quad \text{where } x_1, \dots, x_{n-1} \in X \text{ and } \alpha \in (0, 1).$$

The family \mathcal{F} generates a locally convex topology on X ; see [15, Def. (37.9)], that is, a basis of neighborhoods at the origin is given by

$$\{x \in X : p_i(x) \leq \epsilon_i \text{ for } i = 1, 2, \dots, n\},$$

where $p_i \in \mathcal{F}$ and $\epsilon_i > 0$ for $i = 1, 2, \dots, n$. We call this the locally convex topology generated by the fuzzy n -norm N .

Theorem 3.1 *The locally convex topology generated by a fuzzy n -norm is Hausdorff.*

Proof Given $x \in X$, $x \neq 0$, choose $x_1, \dots, x_{n-1} \in X$ such that x_1, \dots, x_{n-1}, x are linearly independent. By Theorem 2.1(A3) we find $\alpha \in (0, 1)$ such that $\|x_1, \dots, x_{n-1}, x\|_\alpha > 0$. The desired statement follows; see [15, Theorem 37.21]. \square

Some topological notions can be expressed directly in terms of the fuzzy-norm N . For instance, we have the following result on convergence of sequences. We remark that the definition of convergence of sequences in a fuzzy n -normed space as given in [20, Definition 2.2] is meaningless.

Theorem 3.2 *Let $\{x_k\}$ be a sequence in X and $x \in X$. Then $\{x_k\}$ converges to x in the locally convex topology generated by N if and only if*

$$\lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} N(a_1, \dots, a_{n-1}, x_k - x, t) = 1 \tag{4}$$

for all $a_1, \dots, a_{n-1} \in X$ and all $t > 0$.

Proof Suppose that $\{x_k\}$ converges to x in (X, N) . Then, for every $\alpha \in (0, 1)$ and all $a_1, a_2, \dots, a_{n-1} \in X$, there is K such that, for all $k \geq K$, $\|a_1, a_2, \dots, a_{n-1}, x_k - x\|_\alpha < \epsilon$. The latter implies

$$N(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_{n-1}, x_k - x, \epsilon) \geq \alpha.$$

Since $\alpha \in (0, 1)$ and $\epsilon > 0$ are arbitrary we see that (4) holds. The converse is shown in a similar way. \square

In a similar way we obtain the following theorem.

Theorem 3.3 *Let $\{x_k\}$ be a sequence in X . Then $\{x_k\}$ is a Cauchy sequence in the locally convex topology generated by N if and only if*

$$\lim_{k, m \rightarrow \infty} N(a_1, \dots, a_{n-1}, x_k - x_m, t) = 1 \quad (5)$$

for all $a_1, \dots, a_{n-1} \in X$ and all $t > 0$.

It should be noted that the locally convex topology generated by a fuzzy n -norm is not metrizable, in general. Therefore, in many cases it will be necessary to consider nets $\{x_i\}$ in place of sequences. Of course, Theorems 3.2 and 3.3 generalize in an obvious way to nets.

§4. Fuzzy n -norms on finite dimensional spaces

In this section (X, N) is a fuzzy n -normed space and X has finite dimension at least n . Since the locally convex topology generated by N is Hausdorff by Theorem 3.1 Tihonov's theorem [15, Theorem 23.1] implies that this locally convex topology is the only one on X . Therefore, all fuzzy n -norms on X are equivalent in the sense that they generate the same locally convex topology.

In the rest of this section we will give a direct proof of this fact (without using Tihonov's theorem). We will set $X = \mathbb{R}^d$ with $d \geq n$.

Lemma 4.1 *Every n -seminorm on $X = \mathbb{R}^d$ is continuous as a function on X^n with the euclidian topology.*

Proof For every $j = 1, 2, \dots, n$, let $\{x_{j,k}\}_{k=1}^{\infty}$ be a sequence in X converging to $x_j \in X$. Therefore, $\lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} \|x_{j,k} - x_j\| = 0$, where $\|x\|$ denotes the euclidian norm of x . From property (S4) of an n -seminorm we get

$$\left| \|x_{1,k}, x_{2,k}, \dots, x_{n,k}\| - \|x_1, x_{2,k}, \dots, x_{n,k}\| \right| \leq \|x_{1,k} - x_1, x_{2,k}, \dots, x_{n,k}\|.$$

Expressing every vector in the standard basis of \mathbb{R}^d we see that there is a constant M such that

$$\|y_1, y_2, \dots, y_n\| \leq M \|y_1\| \dots \|y_n\| \text{ for all } y_j \in X.$$

Therefore,

$$\lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} \|x_{1,k} - x_1, x_{2,k}, \dots, x_{n,k}\| = 0$$

and so

$$\lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} \left| \|x_{1,k}, x_{2,k}, \dots, x_{n,k}\| - \|x_1, x_{2,k}, \dots, x_{n,k}\| \right| = 0.$$

We continue this procedure until we reach

$$\lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} \|x_{1,k}, x_{2,k}, \dots, x_{n,k}\| = \|x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n\|. \quad \square$$

Lemma 4.2 *Let (\mathbb{R}^d, N) be a fuzzy n -normed space. Then $\|x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n\|_\alpha$ is an n -norm if $\alpha \in (0, 1)$ is sufficiently close to 1.*

Proof We consider the compact set

$$S = \{(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) \in \mathbb{R}^{dn} : x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n \text{ is an orthonormal system in } \mathbb{R}^d\}.$$

For each $\alpha \in (0, 1)$ consider the set

$$S_\alpha = \{(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) \in S : \|x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n\|_\alpha > 0\}.$$

By Lemma 4.1, S_α is an open subset of S . We now show that

$$S = \bigcup_{\alpha \in (0, 1)} S_\alpha. \quad (6)$$

If $(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) \in S$ then (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) is linearly independent and therefore there is β such that $N(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n, 1) < \beta < 1$. This implies that $\|x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n\|_\beta \geq 1$ so (6) is proved. By compactness of S , we find $\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \dots, \alpha_m$ such that

$$S = \bigcup_{i=1}^m S_{\alpha_i}.$$

Let $\alpha = \max\{\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \dots, \alpha_m\}$. Then $\|x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n\|_\alpha > 0$ for every $(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) \in S$.

Let $x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n \in X$ be linearly independent. Construct an orthonormal system e_1, e_2, \dots, e_n from x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n by the Gram-Schmidt method. Then there is $c > 0$ such that

$$\|x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n\|_\alpha = c \|e_1, e_2, \dots, e_n\|_\alpha > 0.$$

This proves the lemma. □

Theorem 4.1 *Let N be a fuzzy n -norm on \mathbb{R}^d , and let $\{x_k\}$ be a sequence in \mathbb{R}^d and $x \in \mathbb{R}^d$.*

(a) $\{x_k\}$ converges to x with respect to N if and only if $\{x_k\}$ converges to x in the euclidian topology.

(b) $\{x_k\}$ is a Cauchy sequence with respect to N if and only if $\{x_k\}$ is a Cauchy sequence in the euclidian metric.

Proof (a) Suppose $\{x_k\}$ converges to x with respect to euclidian topology. Let $a_1, a_2, \dots, a_{n-1} \in X$. By Lemma 4.1, for every $\alpha \in (0, 1)$,

$$\lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} \|a_1, a_2, \dots, a_{n-1}, x_k - x\|_\alpha = 0.$$

By definition of convergence in (\mathbb{R}^d, N) , we get that $\{x_k\}$ converges to x in (\mathbb{R}^d, N) . Conversely, suppose that $\{x_k\}$ converges to x in (\mathbb{R}^d, N) . By Lemma 4.2, there is $\alpha \in (0, 1)$ such that $\|y_1, y_2, \dots, y_n\|_\alpha$ is an n -norm. By definition, $\{x_k\}$ converges to x in the n -normed space $(\mathbb{R}^d, \|\cdot\|_\alpha)$. It is known from [8, Proposition 3.1] that this implies that $\{x_k\}$ converges to x with respect to euclidian topology.

(b) is proved in a similar way. □

Theorem 4.2 *A finite dimensional fuzzy n -normed space (X, N) is complete.*

Proof This follows directly from Theorem 3.4. \square

§5. Some fixed point theorem in fuzzy n -normed spaces

In this section we prove some fixed point theorems.

Definition 5.1 *A sequence $\{x_k\}$ in a fuzzy n -normed space (X, N) is said to be fuzzy n -convergent to $x^* \in X$ and denoted by $x_k \rightsquigarrow x^*$ as $k \rightarrow \infty$ if*

$$\lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} N(x_1, \dots, x_{n-1}, x_k - x^*, t) = 1$$

for every $x_1, \dots, x_{n-1} \in X$ and x^* is called the fuzzy n -limit of $\{x_k\}$.

Remark 5.1 It is noted that if (X, N) is a fuzzy n -normed space then the fuzzy n -limit of a fuzzy n -convergent sequence is unique. Indeed, if $\{x_k\}$ is a fuzzy n -convergent sequence and suppose it converges to x^* and y^* in X . Then by definition $\lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} N(x_1, \dots, x_{n-1}, x_k - x^*, t) = 1$ and $\lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} N(x_1, \dots, x_{n-1}, x_k - y^*, t) = 1$ for every $x_1, \dots, x_{n-1} \in X$ and for every $t > 0$. By (N5), we have

$$\begin{aligned} N(x_1, \dots, x_{n-1}, x - y, t) &= N(x_1, \dots, x_{n-1}, x^* - x_k + x_k - y^*, t/2 + t/2) \\ &\geq \min\{N(x_1, \dots, x_{n-1}, x^* - x_k, t/2), N(x_1, \dots, x_{n-1}, x_k - y^*, t/2)\}. \end{aligned}$$

By letting $k \rightarrow \infty$, we obtain $N(x_1, \dots, x_{n-1}, x^* - y^*, t) = 1$, which implies that $x^* = y^*$.

Definition 5.2 *A sequence $\{x_k\}$ in a fuzzy n -normed space (X, N) is said to be fuzzy n -Cauchy sequence if*

$$\lim_{k, m \rightarrow \infty} N(x_1, \dots, x_{n-1}, x_k - x_m, t) = 1$$

for every $x_1, \dots, x_{n-1} \in X$ and for every $t > 0$.

Proposition 5.1 *In a fuzzy n -normed space (X, N) , every fuzzy n -convergent sequence is a fuzzy n -Cauchy sequence.*

Proof Let $\{x_k\}$ be a fuzzy n -convergent sequence in X converging to $x^* \in X$. Then $\lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} N(x_1, \dots, x_{n-1}, x_k - x^*, t) = 1$ for every $x_1, \dots, x_{n-1} \in X$ and for every $t > 0$. By (N5),

$$\begin{aligned} N(x_1, \dots, x_{n-1}, x_k - x_m, t) &= N(x_1, \dots, x_{n-1}, x_k - x^* + x^* - x_m, t/2 + t/2) \\ &\geq \min\{N(x_1, \dots, x_{n-1}, x_k - x^*, t/2), N(x_1, \dots, x_{n-1}, x^* - x_m, t/2)\}. \end{aligned}$$

By letting $n, m \rightarrow \infty$, we get,

$$\lim_{k, m \rightarrow \infty} N(x_1, \dots, x_{n-1}, x_k - x_m, t) = 1$$

for every $x_1, \dots, x_{n-1} \in X$ and for every $t > 0$, i.e., $\{x_k\}$ is a fuzzy n -Cauchy sequence. \square

If every fuzzy n -Cauchy sequence in X converges to an $x^* \in X$, then (X, N) is called a complete fuzzy n -normed space. A complete fuzzy n -normed space is then called a fuzzy n -Banach space.

Theorem 5.1 *Let (X, N) be a fuzzy n -normed space. Let $f : X \rightarrow X$ be a map satisfies the condition:*

There exists a $\lambda \in (0, 1)$ such that for all $x, x_1, \dots, x_{n-1} \in X$ and for all $t > 0$, one has

$$N(x_1, \dots, x_{n-1}, x, t) > 1 - t \Rightarrow N(x_1, \dots, x_{n-1}, f(x), \lambda t) > 1 - \lambda t. \quad (7)$$

Then

- (i) *For any real number $\epsilon > 0$ there exists $k_0(\epsilon) \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $f^k(x) \rightsquigarrow \theta$.*
- (ii) *f has at most a fixed point, that is the null vector of X . Moreover, if f is a linear mapping, f has exactly one fixed point.*

Proof (i) Note that if f satisfies the condition (1), then for every $\epsilon \in (0, 1)$, there exists a $k_0 = k_0(\epsilon)$ such that, for all $k \geq k_0$, and for every $x, x_1, \dots, x_{n-1} \in X$

$$N(x_1, \dots, x_{n-1}, f^k(x), \epsilon) > 1 - \epsilon$$

holds. Indeed, one has easily that

$$N(x_1, \dots, x_{n-1}, x, 1 + \epsilon) > 1 - (1 + \epsilon).$$

Then by condition (1), for all $x, x_1, \dots, x_{n-1} \in X$ and $k \geq 1$,

$$N(x_1, \dots, x_{n-1}, f^k(x), \lambda^k(1 + \epsilon)) > 1 - \lambda^k(1 + \epsilon)$$

holds. Indeed, for each $\epsilon > 0$ there exists a $k = k_0$ implies that $\lambda^n(1 + \epsilon) \leq \epsilon$, from which, because of condition (N6), there exists a $k_0 \in \mathbb{N}$ such that for $k \geq k_0$,

$$\begin{aligned} N(x_1, \dots, x_{n-1}, f^k(x), \epsilon) &\geq N(x_1, \dots, x_{n-1}, f^k(x), \lambda^k(1 + \epsilon)) \\ &> 1 - \lambda^k(1 + \epsilon) \\ &\geq 1 - \epsilon. \end{aligned}$$

Since ϵ is an arbitrary, we have $f^k(x) \rightsquigarrow \theta$ as required.

(ii) Assume that $f(x) = x$. By applying part (i), for all $\epsilon \in (0, 1)$ one has

$$N(x_1, \dots, x_{n-1}, x, \epsilon) > 1 - \epsilon$$

for every $x_1, \dots, x_{n-1} \in X$. This implies that

$$N(x_1, \dots, x_{n-1}, x, 0+) = 1$$

for every $x_1, \dots, x_{n-1} \in X$, i.e., $x = \theta$. □

Lemma 5.1 *Let $\{x_k\}$ be a sequence in a fuzzy n-normed space (X, M) . If for every $t > 0$, there exists a constant $\lambda \in (0, 1)$ such that*

$$N(x_1, \dots, x_{n-1}, x_k - x_{k+1}, t) \geq N(x_1, \dots, x_{n-1}, x_{k-1} - x_k, t/\lambda) \quad (8)$$

for all $x_1, \dots, x_{n-1} \in X$, then $\{x_k\}$ is a fuzzy n-Cauchy sequence in X .

Proof Let $t > 0$ and $\lambda \in (0, 1)$. Then for $m \geq k$, by using (N5) and the inequality (1), we have

$$\begin{aligned} & N(x_1, \dots, x_{n-1}, x_k - x_m, t) \\ & \geq \min\{N(x_1, \dots, x_{n-1}, x_k - x_{k+1}, (1-\lambda)t), \\ & \quad N(x_1, \dots, x_{n-1}, x_{k+1} - x_m, \lambda t)\} \\ & \quad \dots \\ & \geq \min\{N(x_1, \dots, x_{n-1}, x_0 - x_1, \frac{(1-\lambda)t}{\lambda^k}), \\ & \quad N(x_1, \dots, x_{n-1}, x_{k+1} - x_m, \lambda t)\} \end{aligned}$$

Also,

$$\begin{aligned} & N(x_1, \dots, x_{n-1}, x_{k+1} - x_m, \lambda t) \\ & \geq \min\{N(x_1, \dots, x_{n-1}, x_{k+1} - x_{k+2}, (1-\lambda)\lambda t), \\ & \quad N(x_1, \dots, x_{n-1}, x_{k+2} - x_m, \lambda^2 t)\} \\ & \quad \dots \\ & \geq \min\{N(x_1, \dots, x_{n-1}, x_0 - x_1, \frac{(1-\lambda)t}{\lambda^k}), \\ & \quad N(x_1, \dots, x_{n-1}, x_{k+2} - x_m, \lambda^2 t)\} \end{aligned}$$

By repeating these argument, we get

$$\begin{aligned} & N(x_1, \dots, x_{n-1}, x_k - x_m, t) \\ & \geq \min\{N(x_1, \dots, x_{n-1}, x_0 - x_1, \frac{(1-\lambda)t}{\lambda^k}), \\ & \quad N(x_1, \dots, x_{n-1}, x_{m-1} - x_m, \lambda^{m-n-1}t)\} \\ & \quad \dots \\ & \geq \min\{N(x_1, \dots, x_{n-1}, x_0 - x_1, \frac{(1-\lambda)t}{\lambda^k}), \\ & \quad N(x_1, \dots, x_{n-1}, x_0 - x_1, \frac{t}{\lambda^k})\} \end{aligned}$$

Since $(1-\lambda)\frac{t}{\lambda^k} \leq \frac{t}{\lambda^k}$ and the property (F6), we conclude that

$$N(x_1, \dots, x_{n-1}, x_k - x_m, t) \geq N(x_1, \dots, x_{n-1}, x_0 - x_1, \frac{(1-\lambda)t}{\lambda^k}).$$

Therefore, by letting $m \geq k \rightarrow \infty$, we get

$$\lim_{k, m \rightarrow \infty} N(x_1, \dots, x_{n-1}, x_k - x_m, t) = 1$$

for every $x_1, \dots, x_{n-1} \in X$ and for every $t > 0$, i.e., $\{x_k\}$ is a fuzzy n -Cauchy sequence. \square

Definition 5.3 A pair of maps (f, g) is called weakly compatible pair if they commute at coincidence point, i.e., $fx = gx$ implies $fgx = gfx$.

Theorem 5.2 Let (X, M) be a fuzzy n -normed space and let $f, g: X \rightarrow X$ satisfy the following conditions:

- (i) $f(X) \subseteq g(X)$;
- (ii) any one $f(X)$ or $g(X)$ is complete;
- (iii) $N(x_1, \dots, x_{n-1}, f(x) - f(y), t) \geq N(x_1, \dots, x_{n-1}, g(x) - g(y), t/\lambda)$, for all $x, y, x_1, \dots, x_{n-1} \in X$, $t > 0$, $\lambda \in (0, 1)$.

Then f and g have a unique common fixed point provided f and g are weakly compatible on X .

Proof Let $x_0 \in X$. By condition (i), we can find $x_1 \in X$ such that $f(x_0) = g(x_1) = y_1$. By induction, we can define a sequence y_k in X such that

$$y_{k+1} = f(x_k) = g(x_{k+1}),$$

$n = 0, 1, 2, \dots$. We consider two cases:

Case I: If $y_r = y_{r+1}$ for some $r \in \mathbb{N}$, then

$$y_r = f(x_{r-1}) = f(x_r) = g(x_r) = g(x_{r+1}) = y_{r+1} = z$$

for some $z \in X$. Since $f(x_r) = g(x_r)$ and f, g are weakly compatible, we have $f(z) = fg(x_r) = gf(x_r) = g(z)$. By condition (iii), for all $x_1, \dots, x_{n-1} \in X$ and for all $t > 0$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} N(x_1, \dots, x_{n-1}, f(z) - z, t) &= N(x_1, \dots, x_{n-1}, f(z) - f(x_r), t) \\ &\geq N(x_1, \dots, x_{n-1}, g(z) - g(x_r), t/\lambda) \\ &\geq \dots \geq N(x_1, \dots, x_{n-1}, g(z) - g(x_r), t/\lambda^k). \end{aligned}$$

Clearly, the righthand side of the inequality approaches 1 as $k \rightarrow \infty$ for every $x_1, \dots, x_{n-1} \in X$ and $t > 0$. Hence, $N(x_1, \dots, x_{n-1}, f(z) - z, t) = 1$. This implies that $f(z) = z = g(z)$, i.e., z is a common fixed point of f and g .

Case II $y_k \neq y_{k+1}$, for each $k = 0, 1, 2, \dots$. Then, by condition (ii) again, we have

$$\begin{aligned} N(x_1, \dots, x_{n-1}, y_k - y_{k+1}, t) &= N(x_1, \dots, x_{n-1}, g(x_k) - g(x_{k+1}), t) \\ &= N(x_1, \dots, x_{n-1}, f(x_{k-1}) - f(x_k), t) \\ &\geq N(x_1, \dots, x_{n-1}, g(x_{k-1}) - g(x_k), t/\lambda) \\ &= N(x_1, \dots, x_{n-1}, y_{k-1} - y_k, t) \end{aligned}$$

Then, by Lemma 5.1, $\{y_k\}$ is a Cauchy sequence (with respect to fuzzy n -norm) in X . Since $g(X)$ is complete, there exists $w \in g(X)$ such that

$$\lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} y_k = \lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} g(x_k) = w.$$

Also, since $w \in g(X)$, we can find a $p \in X$ such that $g(p) = w$. Note that

$$w = g(p) = \lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} g(x_k) = \lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} f(x_k).$$

Thus, by (iii), we have

$$\begin{aligned} N(x_1, \dots, x_{n-1}, f(p) - g(p), t) &= \lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} N(x_1, \dots, x_{n-1}, f(p) - f(x_k), t) \\ &\geq \lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} N(x_1, \dots, x_{n-1}, g(p) - g(x_k), t/\lambda) \\ &= N(x_1, \dots, x_{n-1}, g(p) - w, t/\lambda) \\ &= N(x_1, \dots, x_{n-1}, w - w, t/\lambda), \end{aligned}$$

which implies that $w = f(p) = g(p)$ is a common fixed point of f and g . Furthermore, f and g are weakly compatible maps, we have

$$f(w) = fg(w) = gf(w) = g(w).$$

But than, by (iii),

$$\begin{aligned} N(x_1, \dots, x_{n-1}, f(w) - w, t) &= N(x_1, \dots, x_{n-1}, f(w) - f(p), t) \\ &\geq N(x_1, \dots, x_{n-1}, g(w) - g(p), t/\lambda) \\ &= N(x_1, \dots, x_{n-1}, f(w) - f(p), t/\lambda) \\ &\geq \dots \geq N(x_1, \dots, x_{n-1}, g(w) - g(p), t/\lambda^k). \end{aligned}$$

Clearly, the expression on the righthand side approaches 1 as $k \rightarrow \infty$ for every $x_1, \dots, x_{n-1} \in X$ and $t > 0$, which implies that $f(w) = w$. Therefore, w is a common fixed point of f and g . The uniqueness of fixed point is immediate from condition (iii). \square

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